

A Cross Product Analysis of the Relative Importance of Product Attributes on Consumers' Perceptions of Quality

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Abstract

This study investigates the relative importance of product attributes (both intrinsic and extrinsic) on consumers' quality perceptions across durable and nondurable product categories. The test results reveal that consumers' uses of product attributes as quality assessment criteria differ across product categories. Both product features and price, followed by brand name, are the most critical cues used by consumers to infer quality for the particular durable products. For the entire nondurable products, the brand name is found to be more important than price, product features, and other attributes. The theoretical and practical implications of this research are discussed.

Keywords: Product Attributes, Product Analysis, Consumers' Perceptions

Introduction

There has been a considerable amount of research on factors that can influence consumers' purchase decisions. Among various sources of potential influence, consumers' perceptions of product quality have been demonstrated to be the pivotal determinant in consumers' purchasing decision processes (Amron, 2018; Bishop, 1984; Limpo, Rahim, & Hamzah, 2018; Ginting & Sembiring, 2017; Jacoby & Olson, 1985; Shareef, Kumar, & Kumar, 2008; Zeithaml, 1988)

Previous studies have suggested that consumers often have a lack of motivation to gather information about quality (Gerstner, 1985; Zeithaml, 1988), and, in some cases, consumers simply may be unable to evaluate product quality due to their limited product knowledge (Rao & Monroe, 1988). The absence of the motivation and the product knowledge suggests that consumers are likely to rely on heuristics to judge the quality of a product of purchase interest (Kukar-Kinney, Ridgway, & Monroe, 2012).

Various product attributes have been found to serve as heuristics in evaluating product quality, including price, brand name, and store name (Teas & Agarwal, 2000; Dawar & Parker, 1994; Dodds & Monroe, 1985; Monroe & Chapman, 1987; Stokes, 1985). While many of the product attributes are used by consumers to judge quality at various times and for various products, all of them do not necessarily have equal weight. Some products may have only a weaker connection to the quality (e.g., size, color); others have been suggested to possess critical influences on consumers' quality judgments (e.g., price, brand name).

Previous studies of this subject were tested using a single product upon which the conclusions were drawn. However, consumers' uses of product attributes to judge quality may not be the same across different product categories. This paper explores the relative importance of product attributes (both intrinsic and extrinsic) on consumers' quality perceptions across different product categories. To the authors' awareness, studies on the relative rank order of product attributes on perceived quality across several product categories have been minimal. An understanding of this issue may help marketing practitioners to improve product design, promotion, and other marketing activities.

Literature Review

Research evidence indicates that consumers often rely on product attributes as quality assessment criteria when they do not have certain product information about the product of purchase interest (Rao & Monroe, 1988). This also occurs in a situation where the perceived risk of purchase is high (Olson, 1977; Peterson & Wilson, 1985) and when the product involvement is low (Celsi & Olson, 1988). According to Olson and Jacoby (1972), product attributes used by consumers as signals for quality can be dichotomized into intrinsic and extrinsic product attributes. Specifically, intrinsic product attributes are the physical composition of the product which cannot be changed without altering the nature of the product. Examples of intrinsic product attributes include ingredients, features, and appearance of a product. Extrinsic product

attributes, on the other hand, are basically product-related but not part of the physical product itself. They are attached to the product for the purpose of marketing. Price, brand name, and store name are examples of extrinsic product attributes.

Previous research indicates that the most common product attributes used by consumers to infer quality involve price (De Langhe, Van Osselaer, Puntoni, & McGill, 2014; Völckner & Hofmann, 2007), brand name (Asshidin, Abidin, & Borhan, 2016; Dawar & Parker 1994; Dodds & Monroe, 1985; Mieres, Martin, & Gutiérrez, 2006; Monroe & Chapman, 1987; Olson, 1977; Rao & Monroe, 1989; Zeithaml, 1988), product features (Olson, 1977; Yoon & Kijewski, 1997), store name (Wheatley & Chiu, 1977; Konuk, 2018), and warranties (Cooper & Ross, 1985; Purohit & Srivastava, 2001; Rao & Monroe, 1989; Srivastava & Mitra, 1998). Some generalization results regarding the use of product attributes as heuristics in assessing product quality have emerged. For instance, it is believed that consumers are more likely to use price as a signal of quality for relatively expensive products (Olson, 1977; Aiello, Donvito, Vannucci, Wagner, & Wilson, 2018). Most consumers use price to infer quality when it is the only available attribute (Brucks, Zeithaml, & Naylor, 2000). Price is used as a quality cue to a greater extent when brands are unfamiliar than when brands are familiar (Stokes, 1985; Völckner & Hofmann, 2007; De Langhe et al., 2014). However, for a consumer product, the effect of the brand name on perceived quality is more noticeable than that of the price, which in turn is more important than physical appearance (Rao & Monroe, 1989). Store name and retail image have been found to have little impact on consumers' quality perceptions (Rao & Monroe, 1989).

As Rao and Monroe (1989) stated in their review, the generalizability of these findings is in question. In particular, previous studies in this matter were examined using a specific product category. The relative importance of the product attributes serving as signals for quality may not be shared across different product categories. For example, in the case of an unfamiliar product, a brand name may be considered as the most important quality cue. This can be explained by the contention that brand name often serves as a "summary" cue for overall product attribute information (Zeithaml, 1988). Consequently, consumers may simply rely on the brand name as a signal for quality in order to simplify their decision making process. In other cases, consumers may consider price as the most important quality criterion when product quality is difficult to be differentiated based upon other attributes. For some products that intrinsically create greater perceived risk, consumers may even consider warranty or service as the most important quality assessment criteria.

Method

Motivated by the previous research findings and inquiries, the objective of this study is to examine the relative importance of product attributes in consumers' quality assessments across product categories. Four hundred and forty subjects were randomly selected from a metropolitan area. They were asked to respond to a questionnaire related to the product that they owned or intended to purchase in the near future. Each subject rated one product on the product attributes affecting his or her quality perception using a five-point Likert scale. Eleven products representing seven industries were examined (see Table 1). These products were sought on the basis of industry differentiation, product types, and high levels of quality uncertainty. They involve six durable and five nondurable products.

Table 1. The List of Industry and Product Categories

Industry	Products
	<i>Durable</i>
Computer software	Spreadsheet program
Computer hardware	Computer
Home electronics	TV
Home appliance	Refrigerator, home juice extractor
Automobile	Luxury automobile
	<i>Nondurable</i>
Sports goods	Athletic shoes, women's walking shoes
Cosmetics	Perfume, shampoo, cosmetic line

Perceived quality was measured on the five-item scales developed by Dodds, Monroe, and Grewal (1991) and Monroe and Chapman (1987). Product attributes studied in this research include intrinsic product attributes (physical product features) and extrinsic product attributes (price, brand name, store name, warranty, and service). All product attributes were measured on 5-point scales (1 being not important and 5 being the most important).

Analysis and Results

The obtained data were analyzed by taking the mean and standard deviation of each attribute and ranking them in relative order. Table 2 presents the mean and rank order of product attributes related to consumers’ quality perceptions. By observing ranks based upon sample means, we can compare our results with the existing literature. Across the entire product stimuli, price scores highest (mean score = 4.45), followed by brand name (mean score = 4.28), product features (mean score = 4.15), service (mean score = 3.51), warranty (mean score = 3.34), and store name (mean score = 2.75). An analysis of variance on the entire product categories indicates that the use levels of the product attributes are significantly different ($F_{5, 434} = 85.36, p < .001$). Fifteen paired t-tests show that each product attribute is significantly different from all others.

Table 2. The Rank Order of Product Attributes on Consumers’ Perceived Quality

Product	Rank Order of Product Attributes					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Computer	Features 4.35 (.87)	Price 4.29 (.74)	Brand name 3.71 (1.25)	Service 3.69 (1)	Warranty 3.38 (.98)	Store name 3.14 (1)
Spreadsheet program	Features 4.25 (.71)	Price 4.12 (.94)	Warranty 3.8 (.85)	Brand name 3.46 (.95)	Service 3.23 (.87)	Store name 2.23 (1.1)
Refrigerator	Features 4.53 (.85)	Price 4.33 (.75)	Brand name 4.11 (.68)	Warranty 3.36 (.81)	Service 3.12 (1.2)	Store name 2.82 (.95)
Home juice extractor	Price 4.46 (.86)	Features 4.12 (.77)	Brand name 3.76 (.88)	Warranty 3.60 (1.04)	Service 3.25 (.97)	Store name 3.19 (.93)
TV	Price 4.40 (.86)	Features 4.05 (.99)	Brand name 3.81 (.91)	Warranty 3.30 (1.2)	Service 3.30 (.91)	Store name 2.8 (1.18)
Luxury automobile	Features 4.39 (.97)	Price 4.29 (.84)	Brand name 4.00 (.98)	Service 3.78 (1.10)	Warranty 3.12 (1.00)	Store name 2.89 (.89)
Perfume	Brand name 4.35 (.89)	Price 4.21 (.91)	Service 3.91 (1.20)	Features 3.51 (1.11)	Warranty 3.23 (1.08)	Store name 2.61 (1.03)
Cosmetic line	Brand name 4.36 (.76)	Price 4.22 (.88)	Service 4.01 (1.17)	Features 3.62 (1.05)	Warranty 3.22 (1.11)	Store name 2.92 (1)
Shampoo	Brand name 4.31 (.83)	Price 4.22 (1.01)	Features 3.95 (1)	Warranty 3.87 (.98)	Service 3.51 (1.18)	Store name 2.56 (.51)
Athletic shoes	Brand name 4.42 (.9)	Price 4.39 (.95)	Features 3.89 (1.25)	Warranty 3.74 (1.26)	Service 3.56 (.95)	Store name 2.34 (1.12)
Walking shoes	Brand name 4.25 (.84)	Price 4.15 (.86)	Features 4.02 (.96)	Warranty 3.89 (1.13)	Service 3.23 (.98)	Store name 2.8 (1.15)

We further analyzed consumers’ uses of the six product attributes to judge product quality with respect to the durable and nondurable products. As can be seen from Table 2, product features or price score highest for the respective durable products, followed by brand name and other product attributes. An analysis of variance on the entire durable product categories indicates that the use levels of the product attributes are significantly different ($F_{5, 234} = 39.45, p < .001$). Fifteen paired t-tests reveal that each product attribute is significantly different from all others. The test results demonstrate that both product features and price are the most important product attributes used by consumers to infer quality for durable products.

Despite consistent research showing that brand name is used more frequently than other product attributes when judging product quality (Mazursky & Jacoby, 1985; Gardner, 1971; Rao & Monroe, 1989), it

is not as important as product features and price for the studied durable products. However, brand name scores highest in the entire nondurable product categories, followed by price. The variance analysis also reveals that the levels of the product attributes are significantly different ($F_{5,194} = 35.49$, $p < .001$). This finding conforms to the previous results that brand name is found to be more important than price (Jacoby, Szybillo, & Busasto-Schach, 1977; Rao & Monroe, 1989). Fifteen paired t-tests show that each product attribute is significantly different from all others.

Discussion and Conclusion

Consumers often rely on product attributes or cues to make judgments about the quality of a product, especially when consumers do not always have complete or enough information about the product of purchase interest (Rao & Monroe, 1988; Tellis & Gaeth, 1990; Dodds, 1995). Our findings indicate that consumers' use of product attributes as quality assessment criteria differ across product categories. Consumers rely on product features more heavily than the price for judging the quality, followed by brand name, service, warranty, and store name for the entire durable products except for home juice extractor and TV, where the price is ranked higher than product features. The importance of product features in consumers' quality assessment can be attributable to the notion that product features can be sensed and evaluated at the time that whether it contains certain functions that consumers desire. If individual functions are present, they become essential quality indicators. The studied durable products are viewed as less complex because they are frequently observed and used where consumers feel that quality evaluations are not so difficult. As a result of this certain familiarity, consumers then use price as a measure of the worthiness of product features in order to decide the level of product quality.

The research results demonstrate that the rank order of price is above the brand name for durable products and above store name for all product categories in consumers' quality perceptions. These findings are contradicted to previous studies in which price is a less important attribute than the brand name (Gardner, 1971; Jacoby, Olson, & Haddock, 1971; Stokes, 1985) and store name (Stafford & Enis, 1969) when they are present. The brand name is often viewed by consumers as an "information chunk" that contains a composite of information about product quality level and intrinsic product attributes such as price level, taste, size, and shape (Olson, 1978). However, with the quality improvement of generic brands, consumers may not be able to differentiate them from well-known brands. As a result, consumers are willing to purchase generic brands since they are cheaper than well-known brands. This can explain why brand name is viewed as less important by consumers. The store name is less product-specific than price and product features because a typical retail function is to carry several competing product lines containing a relatively broad range of quality. Consequently, consumers cannot really judge product quality by referring to the store names.

The brand name is more important than price, product features, service, warranty, and store name in consumers' quality assessment for the entire nondurable products such as perfume, cosmetic line, shampoo, athletic shoes, and women's walking shoes. The reason for this rank can be attributable to the contention that these nondurable products are more personal and they have social value due to the intensive product advertisements enhancing their brand image. Brand name, thus, serves as the image of beauty, fashion, and professional to consumers. These findings conform to previous studies in which brand name is a stronger attribute than price and other product attributes for evaluating product quality. Finally, regardless of product categories, warranty, service, and store names are less considered by consumers in their quality evaluations.

Future research should involve more consumers in order to have more accurate generalization results. The results of these studies raise a variety of issues to be examined in future research, such as the potential moderating effect of brand familiarity, product knowledge, price consciousness and other behavioral variables on the relationship between product attributes and perceived quality. More research should include more product attributes across product categories, such as material, country of origin, accessories, ease of use, performance, and aesthetics.

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